

The Role of Organizational Learning in Promoting Organizational Success: A Study on Teaching Hospitals in Egypt

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Abstract

Purpose: This paper attempts to highlight the significant role of Organizational Learning (OL) in improving Organizational Success (OS). OL is widely acknowledged as a critical factor for OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Research Design/Methodology: To assess positive OL, (OL questionnaire American Society for Training and Development, 2002) and OS (OS questionnaire Simon et al., 2011). The data of the study was collected from the employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. Out of the 357 questionnaires that were distributed to employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt, 285 usable questionnaires were returned, a response rate of 79%. Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) was used to confirm the research hypotheses.

Findings: There is a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of OL (the dynamics of learning, conversion of the organization, employee empowerment, knowledge management, and the application of technology) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Practical implications: This research contributes to the need for organizations to practice OL in order to be able to meet contemporary intense competition, as this trend is to play an important role in enhancing OS. The study suggests that the Teaching hospitals in Egypt can increase OS by influencing its OL. The study provided that it is necessary to pay more attention to the dimensions of OL as a key source for organizations to enhance the competitive advantage which is of prime significance for OS.

Originality/value: The study observes that there is a critical shortage in OL and that a greater understanding of the factors that influence the OS is of great importance. Therefore, this study is to examine the relationship between OL and OS. This research dealt with OL in terms of its concept and dimensions, in addition to dealing with the role of OL in promoting OS. Accordingly, the study provided a set of recommendations including the necessity to pay more attention to OL as a key source for OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Keywords: organizational learning, organizational success

1. Introduction

Organizational Learning (OL) works as a catalyst to guide the organization in a progressive way. OL leads to enhanced productivity and performance measured through financial and non-financial variables (Imran, et al., 2011).

Succinctly address OL, development, and change by pointing out that organizations are dynamic and must be able to compete in this competitive and global society by ad infinitum learning. While peak performance is the goal, there are limits to human stamina. Thus, it is imperative to understand that human stamina is limited and that employees are not machines or robots. OL depends on synergy, effective knowledge management, and creativity. One strategy for reaching peak performance is to work smarter not harder (Schwartz, et al., 2010).

OL is dynamic as it involves basic elements of organizational development and growth. Organizations can grow in the traditional sense of increased capital or revenues. From a learning perspective, however, organizations grow when there is an increase in shared understanding involving the organization, its environment and the relationship between the two (Holland & Salama, 2010).

OL includes enhanced knowledge and decision making on how to meet performance objectives, improved internal communication and exchange, engagement and cooperation, as well as motivation and commitment to the organization and organizational performance (Caemmerer & Wilson, 2010).

Organizations have used OL as a strategy for achieving long-term success. Therefore, the analysis of OL is important for both practitioners and researchers. OL has been considered, from a strategic perspective, as a source of heterogeneity among organizations, as well as a basis for a possible competitive advantage (Liao & Wu, 2009).

The scientific conception of knowledge in organizations is still in an early stage of development, although a large and growing body of literature on organizational knowledge, OL, knowledge creation and knowledge management is emerging. Most researchers consider that OL is the product of organizational members' involvement in the interaction and sharing of experiences and knowledge (Curado, 2006).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Organizational Learning OL

The term "learning" in English, according to Oxford (1960) means "to obtain the knowledge or skill by study, experience, thinking, preservation, remembering, taking science or finding out manner.

In French, according to (Robert, 1983), "Apprendre" denotes telling something, acquiring knowledge by mental work or mediated experience.

Learning does not mean education, as education is a deliberate process and needs a teacher and the recipient, while learning can be deliberate or unintentional (Moorhead & Griffin, 1995).

Learning is an effective way to achieve the goals of individuals to obtain rewards, prestige, power and/or strength. It is an effective tool to manage change (Robson, 1997).

Learning is a process of interaction between the individual and the organization through mutual influence. It is making the members of the organization learn together increasing their collective efficiency (Torrington & Hall, 1998).

The term "learn" in English denotes acquiring knowledge or skill via study, experience, thinking, memorizing or knowing (Oxford, 1960). Psychologists define this term as an acquisition of a series of responses throughout time that led to change of behavior (Buehel & Probst, 2000).

Learning is a critical variable in the organization's ability to successfully deal with the ever-changing environment, and OL is vital to decision-making at the organization as a means of access to information and knowledge besides absorbing and processing them (Nath & Mrinalini, 2002).

Most researchers have pointed to the importance of OL for the individual and the organization. Learning contributes to the development of a person by helping him recognize and understand others, interact with them and improve his skills in human relations. This improves the experience of life in order to achieve compatibility with the cultural, social and environmental requirements (Argyris, 1997).

OL can be defined as a continuous testing of experience and its transformation into knowledge available to the whole organization and relevant to their mission (Senge, 1990).

OL represents the bridge between work and creativity, playing an important role in getting the competitive advantage of the organization (Brown & Dguid, 1991).

OL is divided into four processes: information acquisition, information distribution, information interpretation and organizational memory (Huber, 1991).

Some researchers defined OL as all systems, mechanisms and processes used to improve the potentials of individuals continuously so as to achieve specific goals relating to individuals and the organization (Fargo & Skyrme, 1995).

OL is the means through which old ideas are superseded and replaced with new ones. It is listening to others and heeding their opinions (Jones, 1995).

OL is one of the important sources of sustainable competitive advantage (Fulmer, et al., 1998; Malhotra, 1996).

OL has received increased attention from researchers and practitioners alike as a means to address how firms respond to rapidly changing environments (Crossan & Guatto, 1996).

OL is a mechanism by which the organization transforms the individual knowledge of employees into social knowledge (Grant, 1996; Spender, 1996).

OL emerges when organizations acquire information (knowledge, understandings, know-how, techniques and procedures) of any kind by any means (Argyris & Schön, 1978).

OL has been linked to many important organizational outcomes such as the facilitation of innovation (Ahuja & Lampert, 2001), the survival and effectiveness of acquisitions, diversifications and foreign entries (Barkema et al., 1996; Hayward, 2002), increased customer orientation (Hult et al., 2000), and the successful implementation of information systems and business process re-engineering to mention a few (Caron et al., 1994; Robey & Sahay, 1996).

The organization's ability to learn and adapt to change has become one of the basic conditions for efficiency and survival of the organization. OL and the acquisition and dissemination of knowledge play an important role in improving products and services (Licker, 1997; Allee, 1997).

OL is an activity and process via which the organization may attain learning (Finger & Brand, 1999).

OL may take place due to the continuous interaction among individuals through learning. This helps them acquire experiences (Hodgkinson, 2000).

OL is considered to be one of the most promising concepts in modern organizational and leadership literature. OL has grown dramatically, generating a great deal of debate and research (Bapuji & Crossan, 2004).

OL system includes vision, strategy, culture, leadership, structure, systems and processes (Stratigos, 2001).

OL is the means for continuous improvement of efficiency and quality, creativity and responsiveness to customers (Hill & Jones, 2001).

OL may reflect the process of learning in an organization among all employees and on all levels. It is the product of organizational members' involvement in the interaction and sharing of experiences and knowledge. Thus, it is imperative for organizations to promote a "bottom-up" philosophy where suggestions for change start at the bottom of the organization and work their way up to the top. This shared form of knowledge implies that individual learning is a necessity, but not a sufficient condition for OL to occur. The information distributed through the organization's members is shared and interpreted in a systematic way. OL is one of the tools that may be used to accomplish the competitive edge of the organization (Ghosh, 2004).

OL is a process that leads to an organization's incessant learning (Thomas & Allen, 2006).

OL has become an important concept for organizational survival in this competitive environment. The notion of organizational learning has been over-emphasized in the literature, because of the complexity involved in the collective learning processes; it has been perceived as spiritual in nature (Yeo, 2007).

OL is the need for information and knowledge sharing among employees. The failure of employees to speak to their bosses concerning potential problems at work is a frequent impediment to OL. This type of silence, he contends, keeps organizations from recognizing, correcting, and learning from their mistakes (Detert & Burris, 2007).

A primary difference between individual and OL seems to reside not only in the process of learning per se, but also in the method by which knowledge is stored and communicated to other organizational members. Generally speaking, if individual-level knowledge is going to have wide organizational impact, and OL is to occur, knowledge must be either transferred or shared (King et al., 2008).

OL has been regarded as one of the strategic means of achieving long-term organizational success. Reviews of the OL literature have noted a tremendous increase in research interest over the last two decades (Bapuji & Crossan, 2004). OL has become an increasingly important area recently (Liao & Wu, 2009).

OL represents a complex interrelationship among people, their actions, symbols, and processes within the organization. It aims to generate, disseminate, and apply knowledge in an organization. It consists of five learning cycles (1) individual, (2) individual/group, (3) group, (4) group/organizational, (5) organizational (Kok, 2010).

2.2. Organizational Success

"Success" in English, according to (Webster, 1974) means end your access to what is best, or access to excel.

In French, according to (Robert, 1983) "Reussite" means getting a new result, and the means to reach or attain higher. With respect to Organizational Success (OS), there is still some confusion and lack of clarity of methodological and procedural frameworks.

Growth is an indicator for measuring OS. It means efficiency or the organization's ability to achieve its objectives in the long term, through expansion, renovation and survival (Whetten, 1987).

Regarding success through financial performance, operational productivity and efficiency, profits, target return, improvement programs in total quality management framework, re-engineering of reference and comparison is a narrow view that does not define success in the long-term in light of competitive markets. Success in the long-term lies in the organization's ability to do better things than competitors do. This is through owning distinct and fundamental capabilities that can not be imitated; besides ability to get on a competitive center of excellence (Hill & Jones, 2001).

OS is the organization's ability to achieve long-term goals and balance between the goals and objectives of the organization of employees (Kenny, 2001).

OS is the organization's ability to coordinate activities in all components linking this to a common vision to achieve its strategic goals. (Dell & Kramer, 2003).

The basic elements of OS may be expressed in the form of an equation: OS = message + strategic goals + outstanding performance (Whitney, 2010).

There are two approaches for OS in all different organizations. The first approach to OS is the economic gateway. It is based on the competitive advantage stemming from the distinct market place. The first set for the performance of the organization is the external environment of the structure of the competition environment industry (Ambrosini, 2003). This includes approaches of forces of competition (Porter), innovation (Schumpeter), and scenario analysis which is characterized by a vision of the future opportunities and environmental threats, besides forecasting analysis of the competitive advantages (Grant, 2000).

The second approach to OS is based on the relatively modern resources approach, which confirms the possibility of looking at the organization as a package of resources to enable them to get a sustainable competitive advantage (Ambrosini, 2003). This approach is mainly based on a study (Selznick, 1957) about the distinctive competencies, and Penrose (1959) that the organization is a collection of resources and their performance depends on their ability to use these resources. This includes the approach of the value chain to analyze the strategic capabilities that can be converted into essential competencies that support competitive advantage analysis (Hitt, 2001).

2.3. The Relationship between Organizational Learning and Success

There is correlation between work, learning and creativity relationship, though the actual practices determined by the success or failure of the organization. But learning is a link between the work and creativity (Brown & Duguid, 1991).

Organizations learn through creative processes to increase their ability to develop complex projects and new products more successfully than competitors. Increased success in new product development can be seen as learning in creative processes (Granath & Adler, 1995).

Organizations of different types and sizes try to be successful in a competitive environment that encourages them to learn binary loop and triple loop learning (Balasubramanian, 1995).

Successful organizations make change integrated with OL, and encourage managers to experiment and learn to find new ways to make decisions (Jones, 1995).

There are three factors related to OL: the good development of core competencies, continuous improvement in the value chain, and the ability to innovate and to revitalize drastically (Nevis, et al., 1995).

The learning systems is a source of competitive advantage for being able to attack the environment in two ways (1) taking advantage of what is available and (2) taking advantage of future opportunities. This can only be achieved through the ability to adapt to driving style, culture, processes, organizational structure. This ability is a critical factor for organizational success (Macmillan, et al., 2000).

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable of OL. There is one dependent variable of OS. It shows the rational links among the variables. The research model is as shown in the following figure.

Figure (1)

Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

The research framework suggests that OL has an impact on OS. OL is measured in terms of the dynamics of learning, conversion of the organization, employee empowerment, knowledge management, and the application of technology (American Society for Training and Development, 2002). Organizational success is measured in terms of organizational survival and organizational growth (Simon et al., 2011).

3.2. Research Questions and Hypotheses

The researcher found the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature reviews that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between OL and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment. The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted in an interview with (30) employees in order to identify the relationship between OL and OS. The researcher found several indicators notably the important and vital role that could be played by OL in reinforcing OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. As a result of the discussions given above, the research questions are as follows:

- Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between OL (the dynamics of learning) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt?
 Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between OL (conversion of the organization) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt?
 Q3: What is the extent of the relationship between OL (employee empowerment) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt?
 Q4: What is the relationship between OL (knowledge management) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt?
 Q5: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between OL (the application of technology) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt?

There are studies in literature that study OL and OS factors separately and within the frame of bilateral relation but there is no study to find that examines these two factors collectively that are oriented at the Egyptian environment. This study aims to contribute to the literature by examining the research variables collectively and reveal the interaction between the research variables.

As a result of the discussions given above, the following hypotheses were developed to test the effect of OL on OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. The following hypotheses were developed to test if there is significant correlation between OL and OS.

- H1: There is no statistically significant relationship between OL (the dynamics of learning) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.
 H2: OL (conversion of the organization) of employees has no statistically significant effect on OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

H3: There is no statistically significant relationship between OL (employee empowerment) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

H4: OL (knowledge management) of employees has no statistically significant impact on OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

H5: There is no statistically significant relationship between OL (the application of technology) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

3.3. Population and Sample

The population of the study included all employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. This sector includes nine Hospitals. They are Ahmed Maher, El-Matrya, El-Galaa, El-Sahel, Benha, Shebin El-Kom, Damanshour, Sohag and Aswan. The researcher excludes Hospitals in Sohag and Aswan. The total population is 5135 employees. Determination of respondent sample size was calculated using the formula (Daniel, 1999) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

The number of samples obtained by 357 employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt is presented in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Job Category	Number of Population	Percentage	Sample Size
1. Physicians	1926	37.50%	357 X 37.50% = 134
2. Nurses	2714	52.86%	357 X 52.86% = 189
3. Administrative Staff	495	9.64%	357 X 9.64% = 34
Total	5135	100%	357 X 100% = 357

Source: Personnel Department at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt, 2015

3.4. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the relationship between OL and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

A survey research method was used to collect data. The questionnaire included three questions, relating to OL, OS, and biographical information of employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Data collection took two months. Survey responses were 79%, 285 completed surveys out of the 357 distributed.

Table (2) Demographic Variables Frequency Distributions

Variables	Number	Percentage
1- Job Title	Physicians	125 43.9%
	Nurses	144 50.5%
	Administrative Staff	16 5.6%
	Total	285 100%
2- Sex	Male	111 38.9%
	Female	174 61.1%
	Total	285 100%
3- Marital Status	Single	79 27.7%
	Married	206 72.3%
	Total	285 100%
4- Age	Under 30	119 41.8%
	From 30 to 45	114 40.0%
	Above 45	52 18.2%
	Total	285 100%
5- Educational Level	Secondary school	99 34.7%
	University	135 47.4%
	Post Graduate	51 17.9%
	Total	285 100%
6- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	93 32.6%
	From 5 to 10	73 25.6%
	More than 10	119 41.8%
	Total	285 100%

3.5. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

3.5.1. Organizational Learning Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by American Society for Training and Development (2002) in measuring OL, which has been divided into five main components (the dynamics of learning, conversion of the organization, employee empowerment, knowledge management, and the application of technology). The 25-item scale OL section is based on American Society for Training and Development (2002). There were five items measuring the dynamics of learning, five items measuring conversion of the organization, five items measuring employee empowerment, six items measuring knowledge management, and four items measuring the application of technology.

3.5.2. Organizational Success Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by (Simon et al., 2011), in measuring organizational success, which has been divided into two main components (organizational survival and organizational growth). The 10-item scale organizational success section is based on Simon, et al., 2011. There were five items measuring organizational survival and five items measuring organizational growth. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure organizational success at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement, ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

3.6. Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach's alpha or ACC, (2) (MRA), and (3) F- test and T-test. All these tests are found in SPSS.

4. Hypotheses Testing

4.1. Evaluating Reliability

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, the reliability of OL and OS were assessed to reduce errors of measuring and maximizing constancy of these scales. To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach's alpha test was conducted.

Table (3) shows the reliability results for OL and OS. All items had alphas above 0.70 and were, therefore, excellent, according to Langdrige's (2004) criteria.

Table (3) Reliability of OL and OS

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
OL	The Dynamics of Learning	5	0.7524
	Conversion of the Organization	5	0.7757
	Employee Empowerment	5	0.6938
	Knowledge Management	6	0.7753
	The Application of Technology	4	0.6644
	Total Measurement	25	0.9292
OS	Organizational Survival	5	0.8789
	Organizational Growth	5	0.9516
	Total Measurement	10	0.9537

Regarding Table (3), the 25 items of OL are reliable because the ACC is 0.9292. The dynamics of learning, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.7524. Conversion of the organization, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.7757. Furthermore, employee empowerment which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.6938. Knowledge management, which consists of 6 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.7753. The application of technology, which consists of 4 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.6644. Thus, the internal consistency of OL can be acceptable.

According to Table (3), the 10 items of OS are reliable because the ACC is 0.9537. The organizational survival, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8789. The 5 items related to organizational growth are reliable because ACC is 0.9516. Thus, the reliability of OS can be acceptable.

Accordingly, two scales were defined, OL (25 variables), where ACC represented about 0.9292, and OS (10 variables), where ACC represented 0.9537.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

The researcher calculated means and standard deviations for each variable and created a correlation matrix of all variables used in hypothesis testing. Arithmetic mean and standard deviation values related to dependent and independent variables of this study and correlation coefficients between these variables are given in Table (4).

According to Table (4), the first issue examined was the different facets of OL. Among the various facets of OL, those who responded identified the presence of the application of technology (M=3.90, SD=0.752). This was followed by the dynamics of learning (M=3.84, SD=0.716), conversion of the organization (M=3.83, SD=0.719), knowledge management (M=3.77, SD=0.741), and employee empowerment (M=3.70, SD=0.733).

Table (4) Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of Constructs

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. The Dynamics of Learning	3.84	0.716	1					
2. Conversion of the Organization	3.83	0.719	0.984**	1				
3. Employee Empowerment	3.70	0.733	0.637**	0.626**	1			
4. Knowledge Management	3.77	0.741	0.650**	0.641**	0.978**	1		
5. The Application of Technology	3.90	0.752	0.592**	0.586**	0.599**	0.620**	1	
6. Organizational Success	3.59	0.829	0.553**	0.550**	0.408**	0.427**	0.682**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

The second issue examined was the different facets of OS (organizational survival, and organizational growth). Most of the respondents identified the overall OS (M=3.59, SD=0.829).

According to Table (4), OL dimensions have positive and significant relation with OS dimensions. The correlation between OL (the dynamics of learning) and OS is 0.553. For OL (conversion of the organization) and OS, the value is 0.550 whereas OL (employee empowerment) and OS show correlation value of 0.408. For OL (knowledge management) and OS, the value is 0.427 whereas OL (the application of technology) and OS show correlation value of 0.682.

Finally, Table (4) proves that there is a significant and positive correlation between OL and OS. So our hypothesis is supported and it can be said that there is a significant and positive correlation between OL and OS.

4.3. The Relationship between OL (The Dynamics of Learning) and OS

The relationship between OL (The Dynamics of Learning) at Teaching hospitals in Egypt is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OL (The Dynamics of Learning) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Table (5) MRA Results for OL (The Dynamics of Learning) and OS

The Variables of OL (The Dynamics of Learning)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Making senior management encourage workers to learn.	0.194**	0.314	0.098
2. Training individuals on the skill of listening and effective communication.	0.059	0.412	0.169
3. Raising individuals' interest in how to learn from others.	0.295**	0.416	0.173
4. Individuals' recognizing the differences between them in the performance of their business.	0.441**	0.565	0.319
5. Individuals' performing the work assigned to them successfully.	0.146*	0.290	0.084
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.644 0.414 39.449 5, 279 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

Table (5) proves that there is a relationship between OL (The Dynamics of Learning) and OS at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R², the 5 independent variables of the dynamics of learning can explain 41.4% of the total differentiation in JE level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of OL (The Dynamics of Learning) and OS is obtained. Because MCC is 0.644, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.4. The Relationship between OL (Conversion of the Organization) and OS

The relationship between OL (Conversion of the Organization) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OL (Conversion of the Organization) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Table (6) The Relationship between OL (Conversion of the Organization) and OS

The Variables of OL (Conversion of the Organization)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Senior management supports the vision of the learning organization.	0.412**	0.553	0.305
2. Organizational climate supports the importance of learning from others.	0.272**	0.415	0.172
3. Individuals can learn from failure and from success.	0.072	0.418	0.174
4. Processes and programs are important opportunities for learning.	0.154*	0.286	0.081
5. Availability of administrative levels to achieve effective communication and learning.	0.233**	0.355	0.126
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.639 0.409 38.594 5, 279 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

As Table (6) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.639. This means that OS has been significantly explained by the 5 independent variables of OL (Conversion of the Organization).

Furthermore, the R² of 0.409 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 40.9%. It is evident that the five independent variables justified 40.9% of the total factors of OS. Hence, 59.1% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.5. The Relationship between OL (Employee Empowerment) and OS

The relationship between OL (Employee Empowerment) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OL (Employee Empowerment) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Table (7) proves that there is a relationship between OL (Employee Empowerment) OS. As a result of the value of R^2 , the 5 independent variables of knowledge organization can explain 18.8% of the total differentiation in OS level.

Table (7) The Relationship between OL (Employee Empowerment) and OS

The Variables of OL (Employee Empowerment)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Enabling individuals to develop and learn from others.	0.207**	0.281	0.078
2. Decentralization and delegation of authority.	0.143*	0.301	0.090
3. The need for managers to train and instruct personnel.	0.186**	0.294	0.086
4. The organization's interest in the management of customer feedback.	0.157*	0.266	0.070
5. Universities and associations should be involved in the learning process.	0.042	0.233	0.054
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.434 0.188 12.920 5, 279 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of OL (Employee Empowerment) and OS is obtained. Because MCC is 0.434, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.6. The Relationship between OL (Knowledge Management) and OS

The relationship between OL (Knowledge Management) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OL (Knowledge Management) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Table (8) The Relationship between OL (Knowledge Management) and OS

The Variables of OL (Knowledge Management)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Observing what others are doing outside the organization.	0.420**	0.438	0.191
2. Workers control of how to achieve best practices.	0.172**	0.287	0.082
3. Achieving creative thinking skills among workers.	1.350**	0.257	0.066
4. The need for an exhibition to test new ways of working.	0.150*	0.311	0.096
5. Having a system for the creation and use of knowledge.	1.251**	0.233	0.054
6. Developing learning strategies.	0.135*	0.294	0.086
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.543 0.295 19.414 6,278 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

Table (8) proves that there is a relationship between OL (Knowledge Management) and OS at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R^2 , the 5 independent variables of knowledge distribution can explain 29.5% of the total differentiation in OS level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of OL (Knowledge Management) and OS is obtained. Because MCC is 0.543, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.7. The Relationship between OL (The Application of Technology) and OS

The relationship between OL (The Application of Technology) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OL (The Application of Technology) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Table (9) The Relationship between OL (The Application of Technology) and OS

The Variables of OL (The Application of Technology)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Availability of an information system that works effectively.	0.194**	0.472	0.222
2. Getting information in a timely manner.	0.514**	0.676	0.456
3. Relying on JIT system.	0.184**	0.459	0.210
4. Availability of electronic systems to support the learning process.	0.043	0.351	0.123
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.733 0.538 81.475 4, 280 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01			

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.733. This means that OS has been significantly explained by the 4 independent variables of the application of technology.

Furthermore, the R² of 0.538 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 53.8%. It is evident that the five independent variables of the application of technology justified 53.8% of the total factors of OS. Hence, 46.2% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

5. Research Findings

The present study on analyzing the role of OL to improve the OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt reveals a set of results that deserve study and attention. The most important of these results are summarized as follows:

1. There is a significant relationship between OL and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. OL plays an important role in influencing OS. Also, OS contributes significantly to reinforcing OS.
2. OL was positively related with OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt; OL does affect OS.
3. There is a significant relationship between OL and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. In other words, knowledge creation, which is an integral part of OL, significantly and positively influences OS.
4. This study concluded that the OL was positively related with OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. In other words, OL (knowledge acquisition) was positively related with OS.
5. There is a positive relationship between the types of OL and OS of employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. In other words, knowledge organization, which is an integral part of OL, positively correlated with OS.
6. There is a significant relationship between OL and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. In other words, knowledge distribution, which is an integral part of OL, significantly and positively influences OS.
7. This study concluded that the OL was positively related with OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. In other words, OL (use of knowledge) was positively related with OS.
8. There is a positive relationship between the types of OL (knowledge creation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge organization, knowledge distribution, and use of knowledge) and OS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. In other words, OL affects OS.

6. Research Recommendations

In the light of previous results, the researcher completed a set of recommendations the most important of which are as follows:

1. Emphasis on the dissemination of OL culture and embracing the vision of the learning organization that require the creation of a regulatory climate. This supports and recognizes the importance of learning to enhance the chances of success and the development of plans and programs, especially in the activation of OL process.
2. The need to focus on knowledge management processes to achieve their interaction and integration with other learning processes, and the establishment of the center of its mission of knowledge management by watching what others are doing, through referential comparison and best practices.
3. Emphasis on investment learning in enhancing the chances of success to increase the efficiency of interaction with other learning processes through the promotion of senior management of learning. Add to this development through the use of active listening feedback, open channels of communication, the adoption of the approaches of teamwork and enabling individuals on thinking and performance skills.
4. Continuous promoting of modern technological applications and good investment at full power, combined with learning and knowledge management programs to facilitate decision-making and implementation processes. Add to this support training programs and the establishment of an integrated information system at the corporate level.
5. Continuous promotion of policies that seek to empower individuals, particularly through the adoption of decentralization and delegation of authority and the alleviation of laws and regulations to enable the organization to have initiative and move towards their goals more freely exploiting opportunities for success.
6. Expanding the powers of management organizations in selecting and attracting workers according to competence and maturity and the need to lay off the excess in the number of personnel leading to achieve effective performance.
7. The need to inform organizations about owning learning organization characteristics, important strategic option for survival and success in a turbulent environment where everything is constantly changing through the simulation of advanced organizations.

7. Prospective Proposed Research

The present study is one of the pioneer works on the subject in Egypt's organizational context. It provides evidence, suggests the importance and contributes to the existing body of universal knowledge in areas of OL.

The findings of the research help OL researchers, as well as practitioners, develop a better understanding of successful implementation of OL. The current study may provide necessary guidelines to understand the issues of OL and OS. Also, the findings of this study provide an initial understanding of the way towards further research in this area. Future research may focus on other important areas of OS (organizational survival, and organizational growth) and OL process attributes.

Further prospective studies on OL and its impact on some variables, such as job performance, innovation organizational, strategic performance, and effectiveness of managers in different organizations can be applied to other communities, such as private universities, school districts, as well as public and private banks.

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